

THE ROLE OF MOTIVATION IN THE SPORTSMAN'S ACTIVITY

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Abstract: This article discusses the role of psychology in any field, any profession, including in the field of sports, and most importantly, the role of motivation in sportsman's activity.

Key words: Psychology, motivation, motive, sport.

РОЛЬ МОТИВАЦИИ В ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ СПОРТСМЕНА

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматривается роль психологии в любой сфере, любой профессии, в том числе в сфере спорта, а главное, роль мотивации в деятельности спортсмена.

Ключевые слова: Психология, мотивация, мотив, спорт.

On October 31, under the chairmanship of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Miromonovich Mirziyoyev, a meeting devoted to the issues of improving the management system in the field of physical education and sports, developing mass sports, selecting and educating talented athletes, strengthening the industry with qualified personnel, and building modern sports facilities was conducted.

Motivation is a process that initiates, directs, and maintains goal-directed behavior. Motivation includes biological, emotional, social and cognitive forces that activate behavior.

Basically, motivation is divided into two types. These are:

- 1) Extrinsic motivation
- 2) Internal motivation.

Extrinsic motivation is motivation that originates from outside the person and often includes rewards such as prizes, money, social recognition, praise.

Intrinsic motivation is the motivation that originates from within the person, for example: completing complex crossword puzzles for personal satisfaction in solving a problem, etc.

МЕДИЦИНА, ПЕДАГОГИКА И ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ: ТЕОРИЯ И ПРАКТИКА

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When we associate the terms psychology, motivation, motive, sport with each other, the role and importance of psychology and motivation in sports and sportsmen's activities is certainly very great. The problem of maintaining and strengthening the health of the young generation is one of the most important problems of modern society. Motivation is the strength and character that allows you to continue to fight against difficulties, problems, disappointments and disappointments. Motivation is the fuel with unlimited power that drives athletes to their hardest workouts and achievements. Motivation is the key to success for every great athlete and any great sporting achievement.

Characteristics of athlete motivation, athlete motivation is practically the same as usual. With a few variations, athlete motivation has two parts. These are:

- 1) Short term
- 2) Long term.

Short-term motivation is the here and now of overcoming an obstacle, making a decision for a specific goal within a certain period of time.

Long-term motivation is a decision to achieve a big goal, a path made up of small successes.

Motivation in sports and athlete activities based on the above considerations. Before any competition or training, participants, i.e. athletes, are given motivation by the coach. In this case, it is appropriate if the trainer is a specialist in his work with sufficient knowledge and skills. Or we can clearly see this phenomenon before any team games. Often before the game (mainly if the opponent team is strong), the coach holds a conversation to increase the motivation of the team and prepares the team for the battle.

According to I.A. Dzhidaryan, the concept of "motivation of an athlete's activity" can be explained as follows: "Motivation is a unique state of an athlete, ensuring that his needs and opportunities are interrelated with the subject of sports activity. as a result, it is manifested on the basis of the goal of achieving a high level of sports results at that time" . Of course, this definition is not the final conclusion about motivation, its essence is explained by the fact that it gives a reference to a sports expert about the reason of what motivates an athlete to strive for a high sports result. In conclusion, not only strength, exercise, training, and most importantly, psychology and motivation play a very important role in sports and sportsmen's activities.

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Great attention is paid to the activities of sports and athletes in our heavenly country. There are many types of sports and the role of psychology and motivation in their activity and success is incomparable. Our honorable president is also carrying out great reforms in the direction of development and improvement of sports fields for the development of the young generation and the future.

For example, if we take the place of motivation in the career of football and football players, we will surely achieve success as they develop and grow, and in this process, motivation will be their greatest strength. No achievement and success can be achieved without motive and motivation, and motivation has a special role in keeping a person full of energy.

The coach of the famous "Real" football team, Zinedine Zidane, said that the first defeat in his second coaching period was partly due to the lack of motivation among the players. Therefore, motivation has a special place in the activities of players and other sports. .

The motivation of the team of players gathered on the field is not only their strength, but the clothes they wear, the skill of the coach, and the greatest strength and motivation for the players are their fans gathered on the field, their shouts, applause and support for the players, but also for other players. It will also be a great motivation for industry representatives. The football players will raise their confidence during the game by reading the readings and, most importantly, by seeing the flag of their country, they will motivate themselves and work diligently to justify the trust of the people.

It is worth noting that, as we said above, not only football, but also activities in other fields, psychology and motivation have an incomparable and inexhaustible place in my opinion. As long as humanity is living and living, defeats will certainly come after victories. Even when a person is defeated, he always turns to psychology and gets the motivation he needs to take a step forward in life. If we say that psychology, motive and motivation occupy a very large place in human life, we will not be mistaken.

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